

Predicting the Price of Used Cars using Linear Regression

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Abstract—The prediction of car prices is an intriguing research topic that requires significant efforts and a wealth of information. In recent years, the vehicle sector has expanded quickly and significantly. The growth of internet marketplaces has brought to light how important market knowledge is for both buyers and sellers. In this paper, we propose to apply the Linear Regression Machine Learning Algorithm to construct a useful, precise model for predicting the price of used car based on the characteristics, such as company, model, year of purchase, and petrol type. Our model is aims to predict the possible price of vehicle by considering various parameters and features.

Keywords—Machine learning, Linear regression, Car price prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

A surge in the number of automobiles on the road has led to a thriving second hand car market. Both used car buyers and sellers are always looking for strategies to negotiate the best deals. As a result, reliable used automobile pricing is one of the most crucial parts of the market. The recent growth of online markets has simplified car identification and purchase for both buyers and sellers, but it has also made determining the car's value more challenging. Thus, developing a model that is accurate and effective at predicting the cost of a used car can be facilitated by the use of machine learning techniques, particularly Linear Regression. This seminar paper explores the creation of a model for used automobile price prediction that is based on linear regression. This study presents the analytic results as well as the data collecting, pre-processing, feature selection, and model evaluation techniques. The study's goal is to provide information about the suggested model's utility and prospective application in the used car market.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several studies have focused on prediction of used cars price using various Machine Learning algorithms.

Mukkesh Ganesh and Pattabiraman Venkatasubbu[1] Using algorithms like Lasso, Multiple Regression, Regression Trees, the authors of this study tried to build a statistical model that would estimate the cost of a used car based on previous customer data and a set of attributes. The forecast accuracy of various models has also been examined

by the authors in order to develop a more precise algorithm for determining the car's price.

Three separate machine learning methods are employed by Enis Gegic [2] Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN). Create a model to estimate the car's pricing. Each algorithm's performance was compared in order to determine which was best for the given data set. After that, the model is included in a Java application.

The authors of the research paper [3], Dr. R. Ashok Kumar and K. Samruddhi, proposed a supervised machine learning model using the KNN (K Nearest Neighbor) regression algorithm to investigate the price value of used cars. They collected used-car data from the Kaggle website and used various trained and test ratios to examine the data.

The study by Praful Rane et al. [4] aimed to predict the price of used cars using machine learning techniques. The authors pre-processed the data, choose pertinent attributes, and used a dataset that contained details on numerous used cars. Three alternative algorithms were utilised in the study to forecast used car prices, and their effectiveness was measured using a variety of indicators. The authors came to the conclusion that buyers and sellers may use their suggested methodology to determine used automobile prices and purchases in an informed manner.

The study by Chuyang Jin [5] create a machine learning algorithm that can accurately predict the appropriate price of second-hand vehicles by taking into account various factors such as mileage, year of production, fuel efficiency, transmission, road tax, fuel type, and engine capacity. Several regression techniques were employed, and Random Forest Regression garnered the highest precision with an R-squared value of 0.90416. The resulting model surpasses previous research in terms of prediction accuracy and incorporates a broader range of used car attributes. This model can be advantageous for sellers, buyers, and automakers operating in the second-hand car market.

III. MOTIVATION

For many consumers, figuring out a used car's resale value can be frightening and challenging. The factors influencing a vehicle's value go far beyond its age, mileage, manufacture, and model. In addition, elements like design, safety record, and fuel economy can all significantly affect

price. Therefore, more exact and accurate methods must be used to estimate a used car's value. Regression algorithms and artificial intelligence can be used to construct tools that accurately forecast a car's resale value. By giving customers a more precise and trustworthy means to ascertain a vehicle's genuine value, this can be a crucial tool for people and companies looking to buy or sell old cars.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The basic aim of this research is to develop a machine learning model, by examining a used car attributes and making the proper inferences, can forecast its resale value. To achieve this goal, a dataset comprising sales prices of various car makes and models will be utilized to train several machine learning algorithms. The methodology for this study includes the following steps:

- A. Data collection
- B. Data Pre-Processing
- C. Model Building
- D. Analyzing

A. Data Collection

In this analysis, we will examine a dataset available on Kaggle that contains information about second hand vehicles. The dataset includes various factors that contribute to the determination of a used car's price. To guarantee its correctness and dependability, these variables have been carefully chosen, and the dataset has undergone a thorough cleaning. Based on these significant criteria, we will utilise this dataset to forecast the price of second hand cars.

B. Data pre-processing

Another important data pre-processing step is handling missing data. Real-world datasets frequently have missing numbers for a variety of reasons, including incomplete surveys, data entry mistakes, or technical difficulties. Machine learning models' performance may suffer as a result of these missing values. Therefore, before training the models, it is crucial to handle missing data. In addition to deleting the rows or columns that include missing values, missing values can also be imputed using statistical techniques or forecasted using machine learning methods. The type of data used, the number of missing data points, and the study's objectives all have an effect on the technique.

C. Model Building

A linear regression model will be developed to predict the resale value of used cars based on their company, model, year, kilometer driven, and fuel type. The model will be trained and tested using historical sales data.

D. Analyzing

To evaluate the model performance, various metrics including R-squared, mean squared error, and mean absolute error will be used.

Machine Learning

Machine learning can be used to predict used car prices by training a classifier on a large dataset of prices and relevant features. The classifier's accuracy depends on data

quality, algorithm choice, and feature selection/engineering. Hyperparameter tuning can also enhance the classifier's accuracy. In summary, predicting used car prices using machine learning requires collecting and preprocessing data, selecting an appropriate algorithm, performing feature selection/engineering, and optimizing hyperparameters.

V. BUILD MODEL

Linear regression is a statistical method used to predict one variable (the dependent variable) based on another variable (the independent variable). This technique involves fitting a straight line to the data points. The main goal of linear regression is to identify the line that minimizes the sum of squared differences between the expected and actual values of the dependent variable, while also providing the best possible fit to the data points.

The equation of a simple linear regression is:

$$y = mx + b$$

Where,

y is the dependent variable (the variable that are trying to predict)

x is the predictor variable (the variable used to make predictions)

m represents the gradient of line (the speed at which y varies in relation to x)

b represents the y-axis intercept (the y value when x = 0)

Linear regression can be employed in both univariate regression with a single predictor variable and multivariate regression with multiple predictor variables.

1. Split the dataset into training and testing datasets.

```
X_train,X_test,y_train,y_test=train_test_split(X,y,test_size=0.1,random_state=1)
```

2. Fitting the model.

```
[ ] lr=LinearRegression()
```

```
[ ] pipe=make_pipeline(column_trans,lr)
```

```
[ ] pipe.fit(X_train,y_train)
```

3. Predicting the price

```
# Load the saved linear regression model
model = pickle.load(open('LinearRegressionModel.pkl', 'rb'))
# Load the cleaned car data
car = pd.read_csv('Cleaned_Car_data.csv')
```

```
# Make a prediction using the model
prediction = model.predict(pd.DataFrame
(columns=['name', 'company', 'year', 'kms_driven', 'fuel_type'],
data=[[car_model, company, year, kms_driven, fuel_type]]))
```

**The predicted price is
₹294197.56**

VI. RESULT

To forecast the cost of a pre-owned vehicle by relying on its unique attributes, a machine learning algorithm, such as regression analysis, is employed. Utilising evaluation metrics like R-squared and mean squared error (MSE), this algorithm's accuracy is evaluated.

Enter your car details to find the current price

Car Name:

Company:

Year:

Kms Driven:

Fuel Type:

VII. CONCLUSION

The market for used cars is growing significantly as a result of rising auto expenses and consumers' inability to purchase new vehicles. A system that can accurately forecast a used car's value and establish its price based on multiple parameters is therefore urgently needed. Such a system would aid in estimating a secondhand car's price with accuracy.

I.

VIII. REFERENCES

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